

A SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON STANAVIDRADI AND STANA KILAK

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda has a very unique concept when it comes to the composition of living body. It believes that body is formed by the 5 elements and controlled by the 3 bioenergies and 7 tissues, which represent different components of the body. Where as per Charak^[1], he mentioned that Stanya is the Upadhatu of the Rasa dhatu, it has the primary role in the development of Infants. The WHO Recommends exclusive Breastfeeding for the first 6 months and continued up to 1 year and more. Ayurveda considers stanya as Piyuasa^[2] or Amruta and Acharya Sushruta^[3] has given brief knowledge about Stana roga, which includes Stanavidradi, Stanashopa and Stanakopa and Breast /mammary gland is accessory organ of Female reproductive system, which is made up of glandular tissue, fatty and superficial fascia which is embedded the overlying skin with the nipple surrounding zone of pigmented skin in the Areola..

KEYWORDS: Stanya, Srotas, Stanyavidradi, Stanakilak, Breast Abscess.

INTRODUCTION

The essence of the Rasa Dhatu, which is produced from the Pakwa Ahara and spreads all over the body, on reaching Stana is termed as Stanya.^[4] Bhavamisra explained about Shadangatvam^[5], in which Stana are given prime importance in Vaksha region.

Sushruta explained Stana as the Pratyanga.^[6] Stanamula and Stanarohita are two Marmas in Ura region. They are of two Stanyavaha Dhamani^[7] related to Stana. Twenty two additional Peshis are present in female, five in each Stana.^[8] Acharya Harita explains that what-so-ever is ingested by the woman, same travels through Kshiravahi-Sira and getting

mixed with Pitta reaches Jatara and then reaches the Stana and ultimately discharged in the form the milk.^[9] Astanga Sangraha, while explaining the Aparā Nirmana says that the remaining blood moves still up and makes for increase in size of the Stana and helps in the formation of breast milk.^[10] Sushruta says that Shudda Stanya is cold, clean, or free from impurities, sweet in taste and free from discoloration, when put in water mixes evenly, neither produces froth nor settles down.^[11] But Acharya Kashyapa without mentioning any physical characters says that Pure milk is that which provides unobstructed, easy and good growth of strength, longevity as well as good.^[12] Breast lies in superficial fascia of Pectoral region, extended vertically from 2nd to 6th ribs and horizontally at lateral border of the sternum and it compose of milk glands that produce milk, and milk ducts that transport milk from milk glands. The human milk consist of 87% of water, 1% of protein, 4% of lipids and 7% of carbohydrates. The estrogen stretches milk ducts and helps them to carry milk, Prolactin helps in production of progesterone and prepare glands for milk production and progesterone increase the number and size of the lobules in preparation for breast feeding.^[13]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To provide comprehensive literary information about stanavidradi and stanakilak mentioned in ayurvedic classics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Literary concepts are collected from Ayurveda classics and relevant commentaries.
- Relevant topic information is collected from other print media, journals, magazines etc and incorporated according to need of topic.

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF STANAKILAK

When mother of wet nurse ingest Vajra along with eatbles and drinks, this is not digested and metabolised due to being non-cereal, undigested and moistened propelled by Vayu and mixed with Rasa reaches the milk carrying channels, which are especially dilated amongst other Srotas of the woman, settles in breast and causes abnormality.^[14]

GENERAL FEATURES OF STANAKILAK

1. Anorexia
2. Indigestion
3. Uneasiness
4. Lassitude
5. Causeless pain
6. Arthralgia
7. Fever
8. Thirst
9. Diarrhoea
10. Retention of urine
11. Stiffness at Breast
12. Burning sensation and Tenderness at breast

CLINICAL FEATURES OF STANAKILAK ACCORDING TO DOMINANCE OF SPECIFIC DOSHA

1. PITTA DOSHA VITIATION: Suppuration and rupture is earlier
2. KAPHA DOSHA VITIATION: Stanakilak troubles for longer period
3. VATA DOSHA VITIATION: Stanakilak cures very fast

STANAVIDRADI

Acharya Sushruta has given special emphasis on Stanavidradi, explained about its etiology, classification, and Specific symptoms according to Dosha.^[15]

Etiopathogenesis of breast abscesses

- Excessive consumption of stale, hot and dry food
- Foods which tend to produce burning sensation /corrosive foods
- Sleeping over uneven beds
- Abnormal acts
- Blood vitiating factors

PATHOLOGY

According to Sushruta and Dalhana - The vitiated doshas reach vessels, especially in the dilated veins of the breasts. The doshas on reaching the breast cause the vitiation of blood and muscles their in cause hard swelling, which itself is breast abscesses.

CLASSIFICATION OF STANAVIDRADI ACCORDING TO ACHARYA SUSHRUTA

1. Vataja stana vidradi
2. Pittaja stana vidradi
3. Kaphajastana vidradi
4. Sannipataja, stana vidradi
5. Abhigaja stana vidradi
6. Agantuja stana vidradi

CLINICAL FEATURES OF STANAVIDRADI**VATAJA STANAVIDRADI**

“LAKSHANANI SAMANANI BHAYAVIDRADI LAKSHANA”

- COLOUR - Krishna [dark]/aruna [dark reddish]
- TOUCH - Purusha [hard, stiff]
- PAIN - Severe, piercing or tearing type
- SIZE AND SHAPE - The swelling is uneven increasing or decreasing alternately
- SUPPURATION - Very slowly
- DISCHARGE - After bursting thin discharge [tanu srava] comes out.
- PULSATION [SPANDANA] - Present.
- GENERAL FEATURES--Bhrama, anaha.

PITTAJA STANA VIDRADI

- LOUR - Ripen fruit of udhumbhara [Pakwaudhumbhara sankashma]
- SIZE AND SHAPE - As like of udhumbhara fruit
- SUPPURATION - Very fast
- DISCHARGE - Sheeta sraava after rupture
- GENEAL FEATURES - Trishna, moha, jwara and daha.

KAPHAJA STANAVIDRADI

- SUPPURATION - Graddully or lately
- COLOUR - Resembles to earthen pot, pandu [yellowish white]
- TOUCH - Sheeta, stabdha
- PAIN - Alpavedhana
- ITACHING - Present
- DISCHARGE - White [sheetasrava] after rupture
- GENEAL FEATURES - Utklesh, aruchi, gourava.

SANNIPATAJA STANAVIDRADI

- COLOUR - Multiple colour
- PAIN - Different type of pain [piecing, burning and tearing type of pain]
- SIZE AND SHAPE - Visham [irregular in size and shape]
- SUPPURATION - Vishama paka
- DISCHARGE - Nanasrava [irregularity]

DISSCUSSION

Almost all Acharyas explained about Stanavidradi, but only Kashyapa explained about the Stanakilak based on the etiology. Stanavidradi are classified based on the Dosha predominance and also Kashyapa explained about different features of Stanakilak based on the dosha.

CONCLUSION

Stanya is very basic source for the infants for their growth, so every women need to take care of their health, especially after delivery, if they allow the doshas to get vitiated by indulging.

Stana vidradi are very common now days, because of the intake of food and routine pressure work of the women, so every need take care of their health by examining themselves standing in front of the mirror, routinely checking about the breast, about their size and shape.

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